

Insights into responses to elevated temperatures in *Solanum tuberosum* cultivars with contrasting sensitivity

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ABSTRACT

Elevated temperatures caused by climate change threaten potato production. To understand heat stress adaptations and variety-specific responses, plants of a susceptible (Cecile) and a tolerant cultivar (Solara) were exposed to elevated temperatures (30/28 °C) for 21 days at tuberization stage. Phenotypic, physiological, transcriptional and metabolic changes were analyzed in comparison to ambient temperatures (21/19 °C). Heat stress caused shoot elongation and tuber weight loss, which were more pronounced in Cecile. Transcriptome analysis of leaf samples revealed a stronger decrease of photosynthesis-associated genes in the sensitive cultivar Cecile, which was associated with decreased chlorophyll fluorescence and an early senescence. These effects correlated with strongly elevated levels of salicylic acid and ethylene. In contrast, Solara showed delayed senescence and a higher expression of sugar and amino acid transporters suggesting an adaptive mechanism to maintain carbohydrate and amino acid allocation. The expression of known tuberization regulators including *SP6A*, exhibited a similar response to heat in both varieties, with decreasing expression of *SP6A*. Solara exhibited a constitutively higher expression of *PEBP14/15* and *MADS13*, which potentially promote tuberization and may support tuber growth under heat. Regardless of variety, a few genes, such as *HSP20* and *HSP70*, were induced by heat and may serve as heat stress marker genes. Altogether, the results indicate that delayed senescence, stable photosynthesis, efficient assimilate translocation, and differential regulation of tuberization pathways contribute to heat tolerance in Solara. These insights improve our understanding of the molecular basis of heat resilience and provide potential targets for breeding climate-resilient potato varieties.

1. Introduction

Climate change, marked by an increased frequency and intensity of heat and drought periods, causes losses in agricultural production and threatens food security (Bailey-Serres et al., 2019; Rivero et al., 2022; Sato et al., 2024). In addition, the predicted increase in the human population of up to 9 billion people by 2050 (United Nations, 2011) together with the reduction of arable land due to desertification and urbanization is posing an increasing challenge to modern agriculture and requires changes in agricultural practices and the development of stress-resilient cultivars (Lippmann et al., 2019; Rivero et al., 2022). This requires a comprehensive knowledge of abiotic stress tolerance

mechanisms.

Potato is the most important non-grain crop worldwide (FAOSTAT, 2022). Potato tubers provide a high dry matter and protein content per hectare, and their water use efficiency is superior to that of the major cereals (Birch et al., 2012). Due to their high nutritional value, including essential carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins and minerals, tubers are popular food and critical for global food security because they contribute to fighting poverty and malnutrition (George et al., 2017). In addition, they serve as animal feed, feedstock for various industrial applications.

Native to the cool Andean region, potato is vulnerable to already moderately elevated temperatures (>27 °C, heat stress) (Levy and

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Veilleux, 2007). Projections indicate a 2–6 % decrease in global potato yields by 2055, with more substantial declines of up to 26 % by 2085, depending on the climate scenarios employed (Raymundo et al., 2018). In addition, heat stimulates the development of anomalies such as second growth of tubers, impairs tuber quality and reduces marketable yield (Bodlaender et al., 1964; Rykaczewska, 2015; Zhou et al., 2023). The sensitivity of potato plants to heat depends on the duration and intensity of the stress, as well as on the development stage at which they experience it (Kim and Lee, 2019; Lal et al., 2022). The onset of tuber formation and tuber filling are considered as most critical periods (Kim and Lee, 2019). Early-maturing varieties are generally exposed to high temperatures for a shorter period in summer and are therefore less affected by heat than late-maturing varieties (Kim and Lee, 2019; G. Zhang et al., 2020). Already moderately elevated temperatures cause many molecular, biochemical, physiological, and morphological changes to adapt to the prevailing conditions (reviewed in Lal et al., 2022). Typical adaptations include increased production of heat shock proteins (HSPs), which act as molecular chaperones and ensure the stability and function of cellular proteins (Lal et al., 2022; Sato et al., 2024). Hyponasty and increased shoot elongation, known as thermomorphogenesis responses, are induced to improve air circulation (Casal and Balasubramanian, 2019; Hayes et al., 2021; Quint et al., 2016). Higher stomatal conductance and transpiration allow to cool the leaf surface (Lehretz et al., 2021; Wolf et al., 1990; Zagorščak et al., 2025). Various recent studies showed a reduced CO₂ fixation rate and a disturbance of assimilate (sucrose) allocation from source leaves to sink tubers upon heat exposure (Demirel et al., 2020; Hammes and De Jager, 1990). The reduced sucrose availability in growing tubers is thought to limit starch formation (Hastilestari et al., 2018; Wolf et al., 1991). However, there are also studies in which no effect or even an increased photosynthetic activity was described (Guillemette et al., 2024; Hancock et al., 2014; Lafta and Lorenzen, 1995). The expression of *Self-Pruning 6A (SP6A)*, a key gene involved in tuber formation, decreases at elevated temperatures, which delays or inhibits tuberization (Hancock et al., 2014; Hastilestari et al., 2018; Koch et al., 2024). Together, these changes have a negative impact on tuber yield and the tuber nutritional value (Hancock et al., 2014; Hastilestari et al., 2018; Koch et al., 2024; Lal et al., 2022; Wolf et al., 1991).

Elevated temperatures and other unfavorable environmental conditions, such as limited water availability, insufficient light, nutrient deficiency or pathogen attack (Guo and Gan, 2005; Woo et al., 2019; Y. Zhang et al., 2020), can accelerate the onset of senescence and thereby limit the growth period (Obiero et al., 2019). Senescence is the final stage of plant development and has been well studied as it is a key trait that affects yield in crop plants (Woo et al., 2018). As leaves age, chlorophyll is degraded resulting in a characteristic yellowish discoloration. Macromolecules, such as proteins, lipids and nucleic acids, are broken down, and the released nutrients are remobilized to developing organs, such as young leaves or flowers (Guiboileau et al., 2010; Guo et al., 2021). This process is regulated by several endogenous alterations, including hormonal changes and the activation of numerous regulatory genes, that play a pivotal role in the onset of senescence (Guo et al., 2021; Guo and Gan, 2005; Huang et al., 2022; Shi et al., 2024). A comprehensive leaf senescence database has been established and currently contains over 30000 senescence-associated genes (SAGs) and 1209 mutants from 148 species (Zhao et al., 2024). The influence of hormones on leaf senescence has been extensively studied. Ethylene (ET), salicylic acid (SA), jasmonic acid (JA), abscisic acid (ABA) and brassinosteroids have been identified as age-promoting hormones (Guo et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2022). Conversely, cytokinin (CK), gibberellin (GA) and auxin delay senescence. For instance, targeted expression of *isopentyl transferase (IPT)*, which is involved in cytokinin biosynthesis, maintained chlorophyll levels and delayed leaf senescence in several plant species, and can improve tolerance as well as yield to abiotic stresses compared to the controls (Huynh et al., 2005; Joshi et al., 2019; Oneto et al., 2016; Peleg et al., 2011; Swartzberg et al., 2006; Xu et al.,

2010). Hence, suppression of premature senescence induced by unfavorable environmental conditions is seen as a promising approach to prolong life span and thereby increase stress resilience of crop plants (Guo et al., 2021; Guo and Gan, 2014).

A recent survey analyzed how European farmers perceive the impact of climate change on potato cultivation and what is most important to them (Von Gehren et al., 2023). Most respondents have experienced consequences of climate change firsthand. They emphasized that developing climate-adapted and yield-stable varieties are among their key needs. To address this challenge, we need a deep understanding of how potato plants respond to elevated temperatures at the molecular, metabolic and physiological level. Recent research has identified genetic loci and several candidate genes linked to heat tolerance in potato (Demirel et al., 2020; Gangadhar et al., 2021; Gautam et al., 2022; Kaier et al., 2024; Koch et al., 2024; Trapero-Mozos et al., 2018; Yeo et al., 2025; Zhu et al., 2021) as well as analyzed physiological and molecular changes (Guillemette et al., 2024; Zagorščak et al., 2025). As the susceptibility to heat varies greatly between varieties (Demirel et al., 2020; Kaier et al., 2024; Tang et al., 2018), this study aimed to deepen the understanding of heat stress tolerance and susceptibility by analyzing two cultivars (Cecile and Solara) with different heat responses.

The present study intended to answer the following research questions: (i) Which physiological, metabolic and transcriptional changes are activated during heat exposure in potato? (ii) Which of these changes are specific for a heat-sensitive variety (Cecile) or a rather tolerant variety (Solara)? (iii) Can we identify mechanisms related to increased heat stress resilience?

The outcome revealed that the sensitive variety Cecile showed a more pronounced heat response with a greater impact on shoot growth, a faster and stronger decline of photosynthesis, a higher accumulation of SA and ET and an activation of stress- and senescence-related genes, leading to impaired plant fitness and tuber development. In contrast, the more tolerant cultivar Solara exhibited increased expression of genes coding for different sugar, amino acid and potassium transporters, and for osmotically active compounds such as proline or raffinose oligosaccharides (ROF) which can help to maintain metabolic homeostasis, allowing Solara to cope better with heat. Here, we present results of a comprehensive study and discuss candidate genes as well as processes that play a role in heat stress adaptations.

2. Results

2.1. Phenotypic changes of heat sensitive (Cecile) and heat tolerant (Solara) potato cultivars in response to heat stress

We performed a comparative analysis between two potato varieties with different degrees of heat stress responses to gain a better understanding of the signaling pathways and processes associated with heat tolerance and sensitivity. In a previous screening under glasshouse conditions, the cultivars Cecile and Solara were identified as heat sensitive and heat tolerant, respectively (Kaier et al., 2024) and were therefore chosen for this in-depth analysis. The experimental design was similar to the previous study (Fig. 1A): plants derived from tissue culture were grown under control conditions (21 °C/19 °C, day/night) for 35 days until tuber induction commenced in both cultivars (Fig. 1D, harvest I, Suppl. Table 1). Then half of the plants were exposed to moderately elevated temperatures (30 °C/28 °C, day/night, referred to as heat) for up to 21 days. During the heat stress treatment, changes in plant growth and development were monitored at four harvest times and leaves were sampled at three time points to analyze physiological, metabolic, and transcriptional changes (Fig. 1A).

Phenotypic evaluation revealed an effect of heat on morphology in both cultivars (Fig. 1B). Hyponastic leaf growth, a typical thermomorphogenic response, was observed in both cultivars, while stress-induced leaf senescence was more advanced in Cecile, the sensitive cultivar. The two cultivars differed in their plant height already under control

Fig. 1. Experimental setup, phenotypic response, plant height and tuber weight in two contrasting varieties under the influence of heat. A) Experimental design. B) Phenotype at 14 days post stress (dps). C) Plant height during heat exposure ($n = 8$). The control and heat plants were measured on the same day and they are shown with a slight offset to increase visibility. D) Tuber weight at harvest I, II, III, IV. Plants were harvested before the start of the heat treatment (I) and then every week during the heat treatment (II, III and IV). Heat-mediated differences were statistically tested for both varieties at the three dps using an unpaired one-tailed Welch t -test ($\text{fdr} \leq 0.05$). Asterisks indicate significant differences between heat and control treatment ($\text{fdr} \leq 0.05$: *, $\text{fdr} \leq 0.01$: **). Similar results were obtained in three independent experiments.

conditions, but heat-mediated shoot elongation was greater in Cecile than in Solara (Fig. 1B + C). At harvest II, seven days post-stress (dps) induction, the tuber weight was not significantly affected by heat in either cultivar. At 14 and 21 dps (harvest III and IV), both cultivars show heat-induced reductions, with a yield decrease between 41–45 % in Cecile, whereas in Solara it only declined by 23–28 % (Fig. 1D). Tuber number and above-ground biomass were not significantly affected by heat (Suppl. Fig. 1A + B). Notably, the tuber number still increased with time under control condition in Cecile, which was inhibited by heat, leading to a slightly (but not significant) lower mean tuber number at harvest III and IV. However, Cecile's harvest index was significantly reduced by heat and tuber starch content decreased after longer stress application (Suppl. Fig. 1C + D), while it was not significantly affected in Solara (Suppl. Fig. 1D). Moreover, none of the Cecile plants flowered, while flower drop off was accelerated in Solara by stress application (Fig. 1B).

2.2. Dynamic transcriptional changes under heat stress in leaves of a heat-sensitive (Cecile) and a heat-tolerant (Solara) cultivar

To unravel processes and pathways influenced by heat stress in the two cultivars, a transcriptome analysis was conducted. RNA was extracted from leaf samples taken 3, 7 and 13 days after the start of the heat treatment and subjected to RNA-Sequencing (using Illumina technology). Data were processed as described in the material and methods chapter (see Suppl. Table 2). A principal component analysis revealed a distinct separation between both varieties along PC1 and between temperature treatments along PC2 (Fig. 2A). Samples from control-treated plants clustered together, however with a clear distinction of individual time points. Heat treatment had a larger effect on gene expression, and particularly in Cecile the separation of samples becomes more pronounced with prolonged heat stress. This observation is also reflected in the continuously increasing number of differentially

Fig. 2. Transcriptomic analysis in source leaves of two varieties with contrasting stress sensitivity. A) Principal component analysis of all expressed genes (depth-filtered and variance-stabilized) ($n = 3-4$). B) UpSet-Plot showing both the number of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) of the analyzed groups (number of DEGs = set size bars) and the number of common and unique genes from the comparisons (number of genes within intersections = intersection size). The number of expressed genes and DEG due to heat treatment were determined separately for each variety and investigated time point. Source leaves were sampled at 3, 7 and 13 dps ($n = 3-4$) from control and heat-treated Solara (heat tolerant) and Cecile (heat sensitive) plants (see Fig. 1A).

expressed genes (DEGs) during the stress period (Fig. 2B and Suppl. Table 3). Thus, 13 days after heat stress more than 4000 genes were DEGs in Cecile. Accordingly, also the number of unique DEGs (genes that were only changed in a certain condition) is highest at 13 dps in Cecile (1802), followed by Cecile at 7 dps (495) (see Fig. 2B and Suppl. Table 3).

Comparing all conditions, 102 genes were found to be differentially regulated by heat independent of time and genotype (Fig. 2B). Among those 55 and 40 were consistently increased and decreased by heat, respectively (Suppl. Table 3). GO-term enrichment suggests a significant up-regulation of abiotic stress pathways ('response to heat', 'response to cadmium ion', 'response to hydrogen peroxide' and 'heat acclimation') as well as of protein-associated pathways ('protein folding', 'protein refolding', 'cellular response to unfolded protein' and others) (Suppl. Fig. 2). Included in these pathways are few members of the HSP20 and HSP70 family such as *Hsp20-4* (*Soltu.DM.01G041960*), *Hsp20-11* (*Soltu.DM.04G008820*), *Hsp20-24* (*Soltu.DM.08G012580*) and *Hsp20-25* (*Soltu.DM.08G012670*) (according to Zhao et al., 2018) (Suppl. Fig. 2 and Suppl. Table 3), as well as *Hsp70-11* (*Soltu.DM.12G011130*) and *Hsp70-17* (*Soltu.DM.04G007430*) (Liu et al., 2018 or *HSc70* according to Trapero-Mozos et al., 2018). These genes were expressed at higher levels under heat stress compared to control conditions and might be considered as general heat markers. In addition, three genes coding for chlorophyll *a/b* binding proteins (*Soltu.DM.02G014010*, *Soltu.DM.02G014030*, *Soltu.DM.02G014040*) involved in forming light-harvesting complexes of the photosystems and *photosystem II light harvesting complex gene 2.1* (*Soltu.DM.12G023640*) were less expressed under heat in all comparisons (Suppl. Fig. 2).

Next, a GO enrichment analysis was carried out on genes that showed a significantly weaker and stronger expression under heat vs. control at the different time points in both cultivars. Fig. 3 provides an overview, showing only those pathways that were enriched in at least two of the comparisons with at least 15 DEGs. A detailed list of all overrepresented pathways and the corresponding DEGs can be found in Suppl. Table 4. This table also includes pathways that were only significant in one comparison or contained a lower number of DEGs (<15 counts). In both

cultivars, genes associated with abiotic stress (especially 'response to heat' and 'cellular response to hypoxia') and 'protein folding' were induced by heat. In Cecile, the biotic stress signaling pathways 'signal transduction' and both 'response to jasmonic acid' and 'response to salicylic acid' were activated by heat suggesting an altered hormone signaling and response.

GO term enrichment suggests a heat-mediated down-regulation of the biotic stress signaling pathway 'defense response to fungus' in Solara at 3 and 7 dps, but not in Cecile. Remarkably, the enrichment also suggests a significant downregulation of the functional groups 'response to light stimulus' and 'photosynthesis', which both comprise many photosynthesis-associated genes, under heat in Cecile at all examined time points, but not in Solara (Fig. 3).

2.3. Effect of heat stress on photosynthetic performance and chlorophyll content

The results of the GO term analysis indicated that heat stress caused a greater decrease in photosynthetic gene expression in the sensitive cultivar Cecile. To obtain an overview about the effect of heat on this relevant process in both genotypes, we used the MapMan-based functional categorization of genes (Usadel et al., 2005) in which each photosynthesis gene is only once assigned to a specific sub-process, instead of the (hierarchical) GO annotation, where a gene can fall into different categories (i.e., 'photosynthesis, light harvesting in photosystem I' and 'response to light stimulus') (Suppl. Table 5). As illustrated in Fig. 4A and Suppl. Fig. 3, the expression of most photosynthetic genes decreased under heat compared to control conditions. Genes associated with 'PS.light reaction.photosystem I' and 'PS.light reaction.photosystem II' were clearly negatively affected by heat in Cecile and this effect was amplified with prolonged heat stress. Among those groups are multiple genes encoding chlorophyll *a/b* binding proteins, components of the light-harvesting complex and the reaction center of photosystem II. Genes coding for proteins active in the Calvin cycle, such as the *small chain of ribulose biphosphate carboxylase (rubisco)*, *fructose-biphosphate aldolase* and *sedoheptulose-biphosphatase*, exhibited a significant

GO enrichment analysis

Fig. 3. GO enrichment analysis of heat-regulated DEGs. Enrichment analysis was performed on DEGs, which were affected by heat (see Fig. 2B). GO pathways shown were significant in at least two of the investigated comparisons and contained a minimum of 15 genes (Counts). The upper panel shows pathways containing genes that are higher (labelled as 'increased by heat', $\log_2FC \geq 1$) and the lower panel genes that are lower (labelled as "decreased by heat", $\log_2FC \leq -1$) expressed under heat stress. The numbers next to the bars represent the number of genes from the input DEG list that were assigned to the pathway (Count). Biological processes related to GO pathways have been compiled to groups (see color legend below). A detailed list of all enriched pathways and the corresponding DEGs can be found in Suppl. Table 4. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

decrease in Cecile at 13 dps (Suppl. Fig. 3). Furthermore, a significant decrease in gene expression was observed for genes encoding components of the proton channel CF_0 of ATP synthase, such as *ATPase*, *FO complex*, *subunit B*, and the *cytochrome b6/f complex subunit* in Cecile after prolonged stress. In contrast, in Solara a different pattern was found with the strongest reduction in gene expression after 7 days of stress.

However, there were also a few genes whose expression was induced by heat. For example, transcript abundance of the *photosystem II reaction center protein D* (*Soltu.DM.05G014760*) was higher at 7 and 13 dps in Solara and at 3 dps in Cecile. In contrast, both *photosystem II subunit R* (*Soltu.DM.12G020760*) and *rubisco activase (RbA)* (*Soltu.DM.10G023180*) showed a consistent heat-mediated increase (Fig. 4A and Suppl. Fig. 3).

For further investigation, chlorophyll fluorescence was measured in source leaves during the stress treatment as an indicator of photosystem II efficiency (Fig. 4B). Prolonged heat leads to reduced chlorophyll fluorescence in both varieties. However, the decrease was steeper in Cecile, consistent with the stronger decrease in expression of genes involved in the light reaction of photosystem II.

The decline in photosynthetic capacity under heat stress in Cecile was also accompanied by an induction of leaf senescence (Fig. 1B). To

quantify the observed premature leaf senescence, the chlorophyll content was measured in leaves of different age of both varieties at 21 dps (Fig. 4C). Overall, there was a progressive decline in the chlorophyll content from the apical to the basal part in both varieties under heat, which occurred more rapidly in Cecile, reflecting the phenotypic changes (Fig. 1B). Interestingly, the chlorophyll content was increased in very young heat-stressed leaves (4th) compared to controls in both cultivars.

2.4. Analysis of metabolic changes in leaves under heat stress

Given the observed negative influence of elevated temperatures on photosynthesis, the effect on primary metabolites such as sugars and amino acids (Fig. 5 and Suppl. Table 1) was determined in leaf samples. Heat treatment resulted in an accumulation of hexoses (fructose and glucose) especially in Cecile, while sucrose contents remained unaffected in both genotypes. Transitory starch levels declined as an early response to heat in Solara, while in the susceptible variety Cecile, it decreased continuously with stress duration, consistent with the greater impaired photosynthesis.

Many amino acids including arginine, histidine, isoleucine and

Fig. 4. Effect of heat on photosynthetic gene expression, leaf chlorophyll fluorescence and chlorophyll content. A) Heat-mediated transcriptional changes ($\log_2FC(H/C)$) of all expressed genes involved in photosystem I and II (based on MapMan assignment), that were altered by heat in at least one of the comparisons. Heat-mediated DEGs are marked with a dot (grey). For a better overview, the identifiers of the individual genes are abbreviated (without Soltu.DM.). B) Chlorophyll fluorescence (F_v/F_m) during stress treatment ($n = 5$). The control and heat samples were measured at the same time and are shown with a slight offset to increase visibility. Similar results were obtained in three independent experiments. C) Total chlorophyll contents in leaves of different ages at 21 dps. The leaf numbers were determined by their position to the apical meristem (with the 4th being a young leaf and the 12th an old leaf). Heat-mediated differences were statistically tested for both varieties using an unpaired one-tailed Welch t -test ($fdr \leq 0.05$). Asterisks indicate significant differences between heat and control treatment ($fdr \leq 0.05$; *, $fdr \leq 0.01$; **, $fdr \leq 0.001$; ***).

Fig. 5. Influence of heat on leaf sugar and amino acids content. The Heatmap displays the log₂FC in amino acid and sugar levels between heat and control at different time points after heat stress treatment. Leaf metabolite contents were measured for each genotype, dps and treatment (n = 4). Heat-mediated differences were statistically tested for both varieties at the different dps using an unpaired two-tailed Welch *t*-test or Wilcoxon rank sum test. Statistically significant differences are framed with a bold line (fdr ≤ 0.05).

tyrosine accumulated to high amounts under heat in Cecile with high levels at all three time points. In Solara, the content of most amino acids changed only little after 3 days of heat. Histidine, isoleucine and lysine levels showed a significant increase at 7 dps, which was attenuated at 13 dps. Heat also increased the content of the cell-protective amino acid proline in Solara at all investigated time points, but particularly at 7 dps (although not significant). Concurrently, expression of *delta1-pyrroline-5-carboxylate synthase (P5CS, Soltu.DM.06G007050)*, which catalyzes the rate-limiting step in proline biosynthesis, was also induced (Suppl. Fig. 4) (Hu et al., 1992).

2.5. Changes in levels of stress-associated hormones and related pathways

The pathway enrichment analysis indicated a change in Cecile's hormonal regulation due to heat, mainly related to SA and JA signaling pathways (Fig. 3). Hence, transcript abundance of several SA- and JA-responsive genes was increased in response to heat in Cecile, but not in Solara. A few examples are shown in Suppl. Fig. 5, such as the *ABCG40* transporter, *PRB1*, *NDR1* or *JAZ1/ZIM*.

Closer inspection of transcripts underlying the different GO terms also uncovered few genes encoding aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic (ACC)-synthases (ACS) that were increased by heat (Suppl. Table 3) (assigned to 'response to jasmonic acid'). Analysis of transcriptional changes revealed that some genes encoding ACS and ACC-oxidases (ACO), which are involved in the ET synthesis, were differentially expressed in Cecile and Solara in response to heat (Fig. 6A, annotation is based on sequence similarity to Houben and Van De Poel, 2019).

These transcriptional alterations prompted us to measure the contents of several hormones and their metabolites (Fig. 6B–D, Suppl. Fig. 6

and Suppl. Table 1). Although there were significant heat-mediated changes in the content of some inactive GA metabolites, GA4 was the only bioactive species which significantly increased in Cecile at 13 dps. The indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) content did not change in response to heat in either variety, whereas the IAA breakdown product 2-oxindole-3-acetic acid (oxIAA) (Pěncík et al., 2013) significantly decreased in Cecile at 13 dps. The ABA content was slightly induced by heat in Solara, whereas it tended to be reduced in Cecile at 13 dps.

Interestingly, there were clear differences in the levels of the stress-related hormones ET, SA and JA between the sensitive and the tolerant genotype (Fig. 6B–D). The ET production was significantly increased at 3, 7 and 13 dps in both varieties in response to stress treatment (Fig. 6B). However, Cecile accumulated on average 10 times more ET under heat than Solara.

The SA content was not affected by heat in the tolerant cultivar Solara and was overall lower than in Cecile, in which the SA was clearly elevated under heat, at 3, 7 and 13 dps (Fig. 6C). This pattern aligns well with the transcriptional activation of SA response genes in this variety (Fig. 3 and Suppl. Fig. 5). SA can be synthesized by two independent pathways: the isochorismate synthase (ICS) and the phenylalanine ammonia lyase (PAL) pathway (Peng et al., 2021). Analysis of the underlying genes suggests that the increased SA levels were caused by the heat-mediated induction of the PAL branch (Suppl. Fig. 7). This is in agreement with Coquoz et al. (1998) who already concluded that SA in potato leaves is synthesized via the PAL pathway rather than the ICS pathway. Phenylalanine, one substrate of the PAL pathway, also showed a heat-induced increase in Cecile (Suppl. Table 1).

Heat triggered an accumulation of JA in Cecile, but only early after the onset of stress (at 3 dps) (Fig. 6D). The amount of jasmonoyl-L-

Fig. 6. Influence of heat on expression of ethylene biosynthetic genes and hormone content. A) Transcriptional changes of genes involved in ethylene synthesis that were differentially expressed by heat in at least one of the investigated comparisons. DEGs are marked with a dot (grey). For a better overview, the identifiers of the individual genes are abbreviated (without Soltu.DM.). Genes were annotated based on their sequence similarity to *Solanum lycopersicum* homologs (Houben et al. 2019). B) Relative ethylene units. Similar results were obtained in three independent experiments. C) Salicylic acid content. D) Jasmonic acid content. Heat-mediated differences were statistically tested for both varieties at the different dps using an unpaired two-tailed Welch *t*-test or Wilcoxon rank sum test. Asterisks indicate significant differences between heat and control treatment ($\text{fdr} \leq 0.05$).

isoleucine (JA-Ile), the bioactive form of JA in vascular plants (Fonseca et al., 2009), was also measured (Suppl. Table 1), but the levels were below the detection limit in the majority of samples. However, under heat stress, the trend in Cecile was the same as for JA. This early increase in Cecile most likely activates JA signaling and response genes, as shown by the enrichments of these pathways (Fig. 3 and Suppl. Fig. 5).

Our data suggest that heat caused an increased SA and ET synthesis and an activation of downstream signaling pathways, particularly in the sensitive cultivar Cecile. Therefore, transcriptional changes of key components of the signaling pathways were investigated (Suppl. Fig. 7B+8A). *Nonexpresser of PR genes 1 (NPR1)*, which is involved in SA signaling showed an expression pattern similar to that of SA levels. The expression of none of the genes that code for ET signaling components, such as *CTR1*, *EIN2* or *EIN3*, was significantly affected by heat, but the expression of *lysine histidine transporter*, which transports ACC in *A. thaliana* (the precursor of ET) (Shin et al., 2015), showed a clear heat-mediated induction in Cecile (Suppl. Fig. 8B).

Both SA and ET have been associated with the induction of stress-induced senescence (Guo et al., 2021). This prompted us to investigate the expression of genes known to act as positive senescence regulators, primarily known from *Arabidopsis* but also from crop plants (Suppl. Fig. 9) (Guo and Gan, 2011; Jiang et al., 2007; Rauf et al., 2013; Shi et al.,

2024). Expression of the potato homolog of *Arabidopsis ORESARA1 (AtORE1)*, *ORE1SO2* (according to Shi et al., 2024), is moderately increased at all time points in Cecile, while *Stay Green (SGR)* and both *MYB domain protein 2 (MYB2)* homologous genes were strongly induced after prolonged stress in this cultivar. Overall, the observed transcriptional and hormonal alterations, together with the diminished chlorophyll levels, imply a heat-induced acceleration of senescence in the sensitive variety Cecile.

2.6. Transcriptional changes in the tolerant cultivar Solara compared to the sensitive Cecile

Our data show that the heat-sensitive Cecile cultivar exhibited more pronounced heat-induced changes at the morpho-physiological, metabolic and molecular level than the rather stress-tolerant cultivar Solara. To unravel tolerance-associated adaptations, we first asked which DEGs were differentially expressed under heat stress only in Solara at all investigated time points. Thus, 69 and 28 genes were identified as being consistently upregulated and downregulated under heat, respectively, only in Solara (Suppl. Table 3). Among the upregulated genes, the chloroplast-localized *HSP70-2 (Soltu.DM.11G011960)* was found, which *Arabidopsis* homolog (*AT4G24280*) is known to participate in

Fig. 7. Expression pattern of tuberization-associated genes. A) Shown are the expression patterns of central regulators involved in the core tuberization pathway, as well as B) additional known regulators (annotation is based on Gao et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2022). The average of the variance stabilized transformed (vst) counts were calculated for each group (depth-filtered ≥ 25). Data were scaled (z-score) for each gene. Heat-mediated DEGs were calculated as described in the material and methods chapter (see 5.6) and are marked with a dot (grey). For a better overview, the identifiers of the individual genes are abbreviated (without Soltu.DM.).

chloroplasts in thylakoid formation, protein import and photosystem assembly (De Luna-Valdez et al., 2019) and to confer osmotic stress tolerance by enhancing ROS scavenging (Ding et al., 2022). Interestingly, *StConstans-like 1* (*COL1*) is also among the upregulated genes. However, closer inspection revealed that its expression increased under heat in both cultivars, with the increase being only slightly stronger and significant in Solara (Fig. 7A). *COL1* is known as an (indirect) negative regulator of the tuberigen SP6A, by inducing its antagonist Self-Pruning 5G (SP5G, Abelenda et al., 2016). Both SP6A and SP5G belong to the phosphatidylethanolamine-binding protein (PEBP) family (Khosla et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022). This finding stimulated us to have a closer look at genes involved in the tuberization pathway (Fig. 7). *SP6A* was significantly downregulated by heat in both varieties at 7 and 13 dps (Fig. 7A). Interestingly, expression of *SP5G* also decreased after heat application, but it was very low expressed in both cultivars (and was therefore excluded from Fig. 7).

Since this first analysis did not reveal conclusive changes that could be linked to the increased heat tolerance, we hypothesized that Solara copes better with heat stress due to a different gene expression pattern already present under non-stressed conditions. Therefore, we next compared transcript profiles between both cultivars under control temperature. This resulted in the identification of 1295 and 2190 genes that were expressed at higher and lower levels in Solara, respectively (Suppl. Table 6). Thereby, genes that are potentially involved in the regulation of tuberization (Fig. 7B) such as genes coding for MADS-box proteins, like *MADS13* (also named *AGL8* or *FUL*) as well as *PEBP14* (also named *FTL1*) or *PEBP15* (Gao et al., 2018; S. Jing et al., 2023) were found to be higher expressed in Solara than in Cecile under control and heat conditions.

Interestingly, also many transporter encoding genes were among the higher expressed genes in Solara, such as monosaccharide transporters, the sugar transporter *StSWEET11-2* (according to Li et al., 2020), a proline transporter, multiple potassium transporters, as well as several members of the Usually Multiple Amino Acids Move In and Out Transporter (UMAMIT) family (Fig. 8). Also, genes coding for enzymes that catalyze different steps in the formation of raffinose oligosaccharides

(RFOs), namely, an *inositol-1-phosphate synthase* (*MIPS*), a *galactinol synthase* (*StGol4*), and two *raffinose synthases* (*StRFS5* and *StRFS7*) (Q. Jing et al., 2023) are consistently higher expressed in Solara than in Cecile but hardly affected by heat stress. RFOs are involved in osmo-protection and are closely linked to an enhanced antioxidant capacity and abiotic stress tolerance (Q. Jing et al., 2023 and references therein).

In contrast, expression of genes involved in JA-formation (*LOX*, *AOS*, *Jar1*), ET-production (*ACS1b* and *ACO2*, see Fig. 6A) as well as of several genes involved in plant defense and signaling against biotic stresses was lower in Solara than in Cecile (Suppl. Table 6).

2.7. Verification of selected candidate genes

To confirm differential expression of selected candidate genes identified in the transcriptome study, quantitative reverse transcription PCRs (qPCR) were performed using leaf samples from an independent experiment (Suppl. Fig. 10). This experiment was essentially performed as illustrated in Fig. 1A, but leaf samples were taken at 6, 14 and 21 dps. Candidate genes from three different groups were chosen: (I) genes that were influenced by heat stress in both cultivars, (II) genes that were strongly induced by heat in the sensitive cultivar Cecile and (III) genes that were found to be constitutively higher expressed in the tolerant variety Solara.

For group I, *SP6A*, *HSc70* and *RbA* were selected (Suppl. Fig. 10A). Expression of *HSc70* was clearly induced with duration of heat stress in Solara and Cecile. *RbA* expression also increased in both cultivars, but the induction occurred earlier and to stronger extend in the tolerant cultivar Solara. Consistent with results shown in Fig. 7A, transcript abundance of *SP6A* decreased in response to elevated temperature in both varieties.

The transcriptome analysis revealed a strong heat-induced activation of genes involved in ethylene biosynthesis as well as in the SA and JA signaling pathways in the sensitive cultivar Cecile. *ACS2* and *ACO3* as genes coding for enzyme of the ethylene biosynthesis were tested by qPCR together with *NDR1*, *WRKY70*, *PR1B* and *JAZ-ZIM* as SA- and/or JA-responsive genes. As displayed in Suppl Fig. 10B, all genes showed a

Fig. 8. Expression pattern of transporter and sugar metabolism coding genes. Shown are selected genes, which were DEGs between Solara and Cecile under control condition (depth-filtered ≥ 25). The average of the *vst* counts were calculated for each group. Data were scaled (z-score) for each gene. For a better overview, the identifiers of the individual genes are abbreviated (without Soltu.DM.). The *UMAMIT*, *RFS* and *Gol* coding genes were annotated based on their best *A. thaliana* BLASTP hit and *StSWEET11-2* according to Li et al., (2020).

similar expression pattern in this experiment as in the transcriptome data (see Fig. 6, and Suppl. Fig. 5), even though individual expression values exhibited a rather high variation, especially under heat.

To confirm higher expression of candidate genes in the tolerant variety Solara as compared to the sensitive Cecile, *MADS13/AGL8* and *PEBP15* were selected as representatives for the tuberization pathway, *MIPS* and *GOL4* as genes involved in the ROF pathway, as well as the *UMAMIT25* and one *P-transport* family member. Overall, the qPCR confirmed higher expression of these candidates in Solara under both control and heat conditions, despite variability among replicates. For few genes there was a heat effect detectable, such as *MADS13* which was decreased after 6 dps heat in Solara or for *UMAMIT25* which expression tended to increase after longer heat stress. Expression of *PEBP15* was clearly decreased under heat in Cecile at all timepoints, but not in Solara

which differed from the transcriptome study (compare Fig. 7B). Further research is required to unravel their function and whether or not these genes contribute directly or indirectly to heat stress tolerance or sensitivity.

3. Discussion

3.1. Heat stress impairs growth and yield stability in both potato varieties and increases HSP expression

Global warming and the associated increase in extreme weather events are affecting potato yields (Gouerou et al., 2025; Raymundo et al., 2018). To gain insight into adaptation strategies to moderately elevated temperatures (referred to as heat) an in-depth study was

carried out with two potato varieties, Solara and Cecile, that differ in their stress response intensity.

Both potato varieties exhibited typical thermomorphogenic responses, including hyponastic leaf growth and heat-mediated shoot elongation. These responses are well-investigated acclimation strategies in *A. thaliana* to improve air circulation (Casal and Balasubramanian, 2019; Hayes et al., 2021; Quint et al., 2016) which have been observed in other studies of potatoes as well (Hastilestari et al., 2018; Kaier et al., 2024; Tang et al., 2018).

In our study, heat reduced tuber yield in both cultivars, with Cecile being more affected than Solara. While tuber starch content remained largely stable in Solara, it declined in Cecile after prolonged stress. Cecile also showed a pronounced above-ground stress response with clearly enhanced shoot elongation. The effect on yield and growth are consistent with the results of other studies and indicate a shift in assimilate distribution with increasing temperature, favoring shoot growth over tuber growth that can be (partly) explained by the heat-mediated impairment of tuber sink strength (Hancock et al., 2014; Hastilestari et al., 2018; Kaier et al., 2024; Lafta and Lorenzen, 1995; Levy and Veilleux, 2007; Tang et al., 2018; Van Dam et al., 1996; Wolf et al., 1991).

The aim of this study was to investigate which pathways are activated during short as well as prolonged heat stress and to identify changes associated with tolerance and sensitivity. Transcript profiling showed that heat exposure activated expression of typical heat stress gene, such as members of HSP20 and HSP70 family similarly in both cultivars. HSPs act as molecular chaperones helping to maintain cellular homeostasis by preventing protein misfolding, assisting in protein folding, or in degrading damaged proteins (Calixto, 2025; Lal et al., 2022; Sato et al., 2024). Thus, their induction can be seen as a general adaptation response to maintain cellular functions in the face of heat stress. *HSc70* is a consistently heat-induced gene that emerged as a heat tolerance candidate in a biparental diploid potato population and has been validated in the cultivar Désirée and its wild potato relatives (Campbell et al., 2023; Trapero-Mozos et al., 2018). However, in our data, *HSc70* showed even a weaker induction in the tolerant cultivar than the sensitive one, implying that additional factors contribute to Solara's heat tolerance.

3.2. A change in hormone balance is a likely trigger for premature senescence and contributes to the impairment of photosynthetic performance

Consistent with previous reports, heat stress decreased photosynthetic efficiency as measured by chlorophyll fluorescence and the expression of photosynthetic genes also in our study (Hammes and De Jager, 1990; Hastilestari et al., 2018; Prange et al., 1990; Zagorščak et al., 2025). Similarly, photosystem II appeared to be the most thermosensitive component of the photosynthetic apparatus (Mathur et al., 2014). However, the sensitive cultivar Cecile experienced a more severe and progressive decline in chlorophyll fluorescence and photosynthetic gene expression than the tolerant cultivar Solara which also exhibited a different pattern of gene expression. In Solara, the lowest expression of photosynthetic genes was detected at 7 dps, followed by some recovery, which correlated with stabilization of transitory starch accumulation.

Elevated temperature can affect photosynthesis by altered membrane permeability and increased ROS production leading to direct damage of components and structures, which inhibits electron transport rates and ATP synthesis (Mathur et al., 2014; Moore et al., 2021). At the biochemical level, photosynthetic carbon fixation is determined by Rubisco activation, efficiency and ribulose-bisphosphate regeneration. Rubisco activation is, among other processes, catalyzed by RbA, which is very sensitive to heat stress (Crafts-Brandner and Salvucci, 2000). Notably, a higher expression of the *RbA* gene was observed under heat in both cultivars, with Solara showing an earlier response, beginning as soon as 3 days after stress onset. This increase could be an adaptive

strategy to counteract temperature-induced inhibition of Rubisco activation as discussed in Hastilestari et al., (2018) and other studies (Moore et al., 2021). Moreover, our data also indicate a negative effect on the expression of ATP synthase proton channel CF₀ and Calvin cycle enzymes after prolonged stress in Cecile. These findings suggest that both ATP formation and CO₂ fixation rate are limited in Cecile by heat, which is consistent with the observed decrease in transitory starch formation. In contrast, the tolerant variety Solara maintains higher photosynthesis levels under heat stress most likely through intrinsic mechanisms and adaptive changes. This may involve an increased formation of osmoprotective metabolites, such as RFO and proline, as well as earlier induction of few HSPs genes like the chloroplast-localized *HSP70-2* and of *RbA*.

Beside the repression of photosynthesis, phenotypic evaluation together with the decreased chlorophyll content and the induction of senescence-associated genes under heat stress indicated an accelerated senescence in Cecile, which was mitigated in Solara. In addition, hormonal and transcriptional changes uncovered a strong heat-mediated induction of SA, ET, and JA contents and an activated SA and JA signaling in Cecile. Based on the described role of SA, JA and ET in senescence initiation (Guo et al., 2021; He et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2021), we hypothesize that the heat-mediated induction of these hormones contributes to the premature leaf senescence in Cecile.

Most studies focused on the role of these stress hormones in pathogen defense, while their role in abiotic stress responses especially in heat stress is less studied. Recently, a heat-mediated increase in JA-Ile and SA levels was found in the potato cultivar Désirée, similar to our results in Cecile (Zagorščak et al., 2025). Although our transcriptome data showed a consistently heat-induced JA response, this was not reflected by the JA levels themselves, which accumulated only transiently. Thus, JA may not play a predominant role in senescence initiation here. It is therefore important to further analyze the role of JA and JA-Ile in acclimation of potato to heat stress as also concluded in Zagorščak et al., (2025).

Our study revealed a strong increase in the content of SA and of SA-responsive genes, which was prevalent in the sensitive variety. SA also plays a promoting role in relation to senescence (Morris et al., 2000; Zagorščak et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2013, 2017). Given the absence of SA induction in Solara, we assume that this could partly explain the different rates of senescence progression between both varieties.

In the present study, an increase in ET levels by heat was detected in both genotypes, but Cecile produced approximately tenfold higher amounts compared to Solara. This was accompanied by a (continuous) increase in transcript abundance of biosynthesis genes, mainly *ACS2* and *ACO2*. A recent study investigated the effects of exogenous ET treatment on tomato plants (Mohorović et al., 2024). It demonstrated a dose-dependent reduction in photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rates, as well as the induction of genes involved in chlorophyll degradation and a reduction in chlorophyll content. We therefore assume that the elevated ET levels in Cecile contribute to a more rapid ageing process.

Research conducted in *Arabidopsis* has demonstrated that ET promotes senescence via the transcription factors EIN3 and ORE1 (Qiu et al., 2015; Rauf et al., 2013). In addition, Shi et al. (2024) described an increase in expression of the *ORE1* homolog (*ORE1SO2*) in senescing potato plants (Shi et al., 2024). In our study, this gene showed only a slight heat-mediated induction in Cecile, whereas *SGR* (also known as *NYE1*) was significantly increased at 13 dps. In *Arabidopsis*, *ORE1* activates *AtNYE1*, as well as other SAGs and suppresses the expression of chlorophyll *a/b*-binding proteins (Qiu et al., 2015; Rauf et al., 2013). Accordingly, the expression of many photosynthesis-associated genes, including chlorophyll *a/b* binding proteins, decreased strongly with prolonged heat stress in Cecile.

Both SA and ET interact at the molecular level, which is well studied in *A. thaliana* and it has been shown that NPR1 (transcriptional regulator involved in SA signaling) and EIN3 (transcription factor involved in ET signaling) converge in senescing leaves Wang et al. (2021); Yu et al.

(2021). Ramšak et al. (2018) confirmed the role of EIN3 and NPR1 in potato as interfaces between ET and SA signaling during pathogen defense. In our study, both *NPR1* expression and SA contents showed a clear heat-stimulated increase in Cecile at all investigated time points, but not in Solara. We did not detect a heat-mediated differential expression of *StEIN3* orthologs. However, expression of *EIN3* might follow different kinetics, and EIN3 levels can also be regulated at the post-translational level. Nonetheless, the interaction between SA and ET is quite likely as both biosynthesis and signaling pathways become strongly activated by heat in the heat-sensitive cultivar.

Based on our results and the discussed literature, we assume that elevated ET levels elicit chlorophyll degradation and leaf senescence through interaction with SA and contribute to the stronger repression of photosynthetic gene expression under heat stress in the sensitive variety Cecile. However, this hypothesis requires further functional studies.

3.3. In Solara, the downstream regulation of tuber formation could be less impaired and assimilate transport could be maintained under heat

In recent years, many central tuberization regulators have been identified and studied (summarized in Kondhare et al., 2020; Zierer et al., 2021). *SP6A*, is a key regulator in the initiation of tuber formation under favorable conditions (Navarro et al., 2011) and overexpression compensates for heat-mediated yield decline (Koch et al., 2024). In our study, *SP6A* expression was reduced under heat stress similar to previous studies (Hancock et al., 2014; Koch et al., 2024; Zagorščak et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2022). However, the differences in tuber yield observed between both genotypes cannot be attributed to *SP6A*, because its expression was similarly repressed in both.

Tuberization is also controlled by PHYB (Jackson et al., 1998). Heat has no significant effect on the expression of the *StPHYB* gene as demonstrated previously for the *AtPHYB* homolog (Jung et al., 2016). They showed that the PHYB (protein) acts as a thermosensor. Heat accelerates the switch to the inactive form of PHYB and therefore impairs its activity. In potato, PHYB stabilizes COL1 that negatively influences the expression of *SP6A* (Abelenda et al., 2016). *COL1* expression was induced by heat in our study and may be seen as a compensatory mechanism to combat its increased degradation. The induction of *COL1* most likely contributes to heat-mediated repression of *SP6A*. The expression of the positive regulator *BEL5*, which acts further upstream in the tuberization signaling pathway and activates the expression of *SP6A* and *CDF1* (Kondhare et al., 2019; Sharma et al., 2016), was slightly lower in heat, which is also consistent with other findings (Guillemette et al., 2024; Hastilestari et al., 2018). *FKF1* and *GI* also showed a slightly reduced expression in our data set, even though they are thought to negatively affect tuberization (Kondhare et al., 2020; Zierer et al., 2021). It is therefore important to better understand how heat affects individual components of the tuberization pathway and their interaction as this eventually has a strong influence on tuber yield.

Interestingly, two other FT genes, *PEBP14* and *PEBP15*, had 2-5 times higher expression levels in Solara compared to Cecile both under control and heat conditions. Their expression level decreased by heat application, especially in Cecile as also reported by Zhang et al. (2022). While the function of *PEBP15* has not yet been investigated, *PEBP14* (*StFTL1* according to S. Jing et al., 2023) was identified as a positive regulator of tuber formation using a transgenic approach (S. Jing et al., 2023). Hence, its overexpression resulted in an increased number of tubers and higher yield, similar to overexpression of *SP6A* (Koch et al., 2024).

We also found that the expression of several *MADS* genes was clearly higher in Solara than in Cecile. While there are no functional studies on the role of *MADS12* and *MADS117* in potato yet, *MADS13* represents an interesting candidate for further studies (Gao et al., 2018). Previous studies demonstrated that the *MADS13* homologs in rice (*OsMADS14*) and *A. thaliana* (*AtFUL/AtAGL8*) are likely subjected to regulation by their respective FT homologs Hd3a and FT (Kim et al., 2007; Kobayashi et al., 2012; Teper-Bamnlker and Samach, 2005). A recent study in

potato showed that the expression of the *MADS13* gene is induced by *ABA insensitive 5-Like 1/ABI5-like 1 (ABL1)*, which interacts with FT homologs, including *SP6A* (Jing et al., 2022), while Gao et al., (2018) suggested that *MADS13* acts downstream of *SP6A*.

Together, our study shows that expression of genes within the “narrow” tuberization pathway was not differently affected in the selected varieties. Instead, higher expression of regulators acting presumably downstream of *SP6A* and higher activity of other FTs, like *PEBP14* and *15*, may contribute to sustain tuber formation and growth under heat conditions.

In addition to the genotypic differences in the tuberization signaling, several genes coding for transporters were identified that are expressed at higher levels in Solara in control and heat conditions. These include *StSWEET11-2*, coding for a sucrose exporter that plays a central role in phloem loading in leaves (Abelenda et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2012). Although its role in the heat response has not yet been investigated, a recent review emphasizes the potential of *SWEET* family members as promising breeding targets for increasing tolerance to abiotic stress (Gautam et al., 2022). In addition, the increased expression of three *Tonoplast Monosaccharide Transporter (TMT)*-encoding genes that are homologous to *AtTMT2* (Wormit et al., 2007) indicates that Solara possesses a more efficient system to maintain sugar homeostasis and transport under stressful conditions (Saddhe et al., 2021; Wormit et al., 2007).

Another interesting observation was the increased expression of several *UMAMIT* coding genes in Solara. These transporters play a role in the redistribution of amino acids and thus the relocation of bound nitrogen (Cao et al., 2025; Zhao et al., 2021). Our metabolic analyses revealed a higher accumulation of free amino acids under heat stress in both cultivars, whereas this response was less pronounced in Solara. A notable finding is the consistency of these changes with earlier studies, which reported an increased accumulation of histidine, isoleucine, lysine and arginine, among other amino acids, under heat stress conditions (Demirel et al., 2020; Zagorščak et al., 2025). These amino acids thus exhibit a certain conserved response pattern across different studies. Accordingly, the enhanced expression of multiple *UMAMIT* encoding genes in Solara may suggest a more efficient nitrogen homeostasis, for instance through enhanced amino acid remobilization and could positively impact Solara's ability to adapt to stress. An increase in *UMAMIT* activity could explain the reduced amino acid accumulation in Solara, as well as why it is more pronounced in Cecile. However, the role of both the increased accumulation of specific amino acids and of the *UMAMITs* for heat stress adaptations clearly deserves deeper analyses.

4. Conclusion

In light of global warming, there is an urgent need to develop climate-adapted crops, which requires knowledge of the processes and identification of potential target genes that could be used in breeding programs. Our study confirmed that moderate heat stress affects the plant growth, metabolism and gene expression of potato plants, but uncovered that there are large variety-specific differences in the stress response. Cecile as sensitive variety exhibited strong stress responses with clear symptoms, i.e., premature leaf senescence and a strong impairment of its photosynthetic performance, which all resulted in tuber yield reduction. In contrast, the more tolerant variety Solara, exhibited physiological and molecular adaptations to heat that eventually caused a lower heat-induced yield decline. In particular, the increased expression of HSPs, osmolyte-producing enzymes, transporters and regulators involved in tuberization signaling could contribute to increased stress tolerance, sustained assimilate production, translocation and tuber growth. Furthermore, our data suggest that the accumulation of stress hormones SA and ET and the activation of downstream signaling pathways trigger premature leaf senescence under heat in the sensitive variety, further limiting photosynthetic performance and yield.

Thus, our results provide valuable insights into the physiological and molecular mechanisms of potato responses to heat and uncovered differences associated with heat tolerance or sensitivity.

5. Materials and methods

5.1. Plant cultivation, experimental design, and sampling

Potato (*S. tuberosum*) cultivars (Solara and Cecile) were obtained from Bioplant (Germany) and HZPC Holland BV (Netherlands). Plantlets were propagated in tissue culture on MS medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) containing 2 % (w/v) sucrose under conditions of 16 h light and 8 h darkness at 21 °C. From each variety 20 plants were first transferred to 0.5 L pots filled with nutrient-poor substrate (P-Type, Hawita, Vechta, Germany) and were further cultivated in a growth chamber with 16 h light (light intensity was approx. 400 $\mu\text{mol quanta m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) at 21 °C and 8 h darkness at 19 °C. After 7 days the plants were transferred to 3.5 L pots with universal substrate (T-Type, Hawita, Vechta, Germany). To confirm tuberization in both varieties, six plants were harvested 35 days after transfer to the climate chamber. Half the remaining plants were subjected to elevated temperatures (30/28 °C, day/night) in a neighboring climate chamber for 21 days. The plants were watered daily to avoid additional drought stress and relative air humidity was approx. 65 %. The plants were randomly placed. Non-invasive methods, such as measuring plant height or recording chlorophyll fluorescence were performed continuously throughout the stress period. Plant height was measured from the lowest internode to the shoot apical meristem with a folding ruler. Sampling of source leaves was carried out at 2 p.m. (after 8 h of light). For chlorophyll and ET measurements, the leaves were sampled with a cork borer. For RNA isolation, hormone, sugar and amino acid analysis, two whole leaves were harvested. To investigate the effect of heat on tuber weight, 4 plants of each variety were harvested every week at their respective growing temperatures.

5.2. Chlorophyll fluorescence measurements

Chlorophyll fluorescence was determined in source leaves using a FluorPen FP110 device (PSI, Czech Republic). For each variety and treatment temperature, two leaves of five plants were measured as technical and biological replicates. Fv/Fm was measured after a dark incubation of approx. 15 min.

5.3. Chlorophyll measurements

Chlorophyll was extracted by incubating sampled leaf disks (0.5 cm²) in 95 % ethanol at 80 °C for 1 h. Chlorophyll content was determined according to (Lichtenthaler and Buschmann, 2001). Leaves of different age were sampled from six plants each.

5.4. Metabolomics

For the determination of source leaf and tuber sugar content, powdered material (approx. 25 mg leaf material and approx. 50 mg tuber material) was extracted with 0.5 mL 80 % (v/v) ethanol and incubated at 80 °C for 1 h. After centrifugation the supernatants were evaporated to dryness at 40 °C and resolved in 300 μL water. These were used for the measurement of soluble sugars and amino acids. The pellet was incubated with 0.2 M KOH at 95 °C for 1 h and pH value was adjusted to 5.5 by adding 1 M acetic acid. Polymeric molecules of starch were broken down to glucose monomer units by treatment with amyloglucosidase (1 mg/mL in 50 mM sodium acetate buffer) overnight. The sugars were determined photometrically as described previously (Smith and Zeeman, 2006).

For the determination of amino acid contents, 10 μL extracts were mixed with 80 μL borate buffer (200 mM, pH 8.8) and derivatized with 10 μL 6-aminoquinolyl-N-hydroxysuccinimidyl carbamate (AQC)

solution by heating it at 55 °C for 10 min. The samples were measured and quantified using standard samples on a Dionex P680-HPLC system with an RF 2000 fluorescence detector controlled by Chromeleon v6.8 (Dionex, Sunnyvale, CA, USA) as described previously (Obata et al., 2020).

Leaf samples were derived from source leaves of four different plants at each dps and temperature. The tuber parenchyma samples of two tubers of four plants each were pooled.

5.5. Hormonomics

Leaf samples were harvested after 3, 7 and 13 days of heat stress. To determine the hormone content, two whole leaves taken from four plants each were sampled, ground and freeze-dried for subsequent measurements.

Concentration of ABA, IAA and its metabolites (indole-3-acetyl-aspartate - IAA-Asp, indole-3-acetyl-glutamate - IAA-Glu and oxIAA), jasmonates (JA, JA-Ile, *cis*-(+)-12-oxo-phytodienoic acid - *cis*-OPDA) and SA were determined in 2 mg of freeze-dried potato tissue according to the method described by Floková et al. (2014) and modified by Široká et al., (2022). The samples were extracted in cold 1 mol/L formic acid in 10 % aqueous methanol with the addition of internal standards labelled with stable isotopes (5 pmol of [¹³C₆]oxIAA, [¹³C₆]IAA-Asp, [¹³C₆]IAA-Glu and [²H₂]JA-Ile, 10 pmol of [¹³C₆]IAA, [²H₅]OPDA and [²H₆]JA and [²H₄]ABA, and 20 pmol of [²H₄]SA) purchased from OlChemIm (Czech Republic) or Sigma Aldrich (USA). Whole extracts were purified on Oasis HLB solid phase extraction columns (1 cc/30 mg, Waters) according to the described protocol (Floková et al., 2014). The analysis was performed on a 1260 Infinity II LC/SFC hybrid system, coupled to an Agilent 6495B Triple Quadrupole LC/MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) using the settings described (Široká et al., 2022).

Two extraction and purification protocols were tested with regard to find optimized sample weight (2–10 mg DW) and conditions for GA isolation from the complex plant sample (matrix effects study). The best results were achieved with 2 mg DW potato tissue that was extracted and purified as follows: tissue samples were ground to a fine consistency using 2.7-mm zirconium oxide beads (Next Advance Inc., USA) and a MM 400 vibration mill (Retsch, Germany) at a frequency of 27 Hz for 3 min with 1 mL of ice-cold 80 % acetonitrile containing 5 % formic acid as extraction solution (Urbanová et al., 2013). The samples were then extracted overnight at 4 °C using a benchtop laboratory rotator Stuart SB3 (Bibby Scientific, UK) after adding internal gibberellins standards ([²H₂]GA1, [²H₂]GA4, [²H₂]GA6, [²H₂]GA9, [²H₂]GA19, [²H₂]GA20, [²H₂]GA29 and [²H₂]GA44) purchased from OlChemIm, Czech Republic. The homogenates were centrifuged at 36 670 g and 4 °C for 10 min, corresponding supernatants were further purified using mixed-mode SPE cartridges (Waters, Ireland) and analyzed by ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS) using Acquity UPLC I-Class PLUS chromatographic system coupled to Xevo® TQ-XS (both Waters, USA). GAs were detected using multiple-reaction monitoring mode of the transition of the ion [M–H][–] to the appropriate product ion. Masslynx 4.2 software (Waters, USA) was used to analyze the data, and the standard isotope dilution method (Rittenberg and Foster, 1940) was used to quantify the GAs levels.

Measurement of leaf-emitted ET was conducted in different experiments and repeated several times, yielding similar results. Leaves from four control and heat-treated plants were sampled with a cork borer (approx. 0.3 cm²). Each of the four biological replicates was measured four times as technical replicates. Leaf discs were floated on water in a Petri dish overnight at a control or heat temperature to recover from injury caused by sampling. Subsequently, they were transferred into 6 mL glass reaction tubes containing 25 mM 2-(N-morpholino)-ethanesulfonic acid (MES) buffer (pH 5.5), the vials were sealed with rubber plugs and shaken (120 rpm) for 5 h at 21 °C or 30 °C, respectively. To determine the ET content, 1 mL of the gas phase was sampled with a

syringe and analyzed with a GC-flame ionization detector (FID) (Shimadzu, GC-2014). Data analyses were performed using Shimadzu Lab-Solutions Lite software.

5.6. RNA extraction, sequencing and bioinformatic analyses

The same leaf samples used to measure the hormones via UHPLC/MS-MS were also used for the transcriptomic analysis. RNA was extracted from powdered material (approx. 50 mg) according to Logemann et al. (1987) and paired-end sequenced by a service provider (Illumina NovaSeq 6000; Novogene, Cambridge, UK).

Raw sequence reads were quality controlled using FastQC (v.0.11.9) (Andrews, 2010) and MultiQC (v.1.11) (Ewels et al., 2016). Trimming for known adapter sequences and quality filtering were conducted using BBDuk (v38.90) (Bushnell, 2014). A k-mer length of 23 was set, allowing a minimum k-mer length of 11 and 1 mismatch. Additionally, reads were filtered based on read quality (≥ 30) and length (≥ 35). To verify successful trimming and filtering, a quality check was performed using FastQC and MultiQC. Cleaned reads were mapped to the reference genome DM 1–3516 R44 potato v6.1 (Pham et al., 2020) using STAR (v.2.7.9a) (Dobin et al., 2013). Uniquely mapped reads were quantified at the gene level using featureCounts (v.2.0.2) (Liao et al., 2014). All programs were used under Linux (Ubuntu v20.04 LTS).

The principal component analysis was executed using a filter for expressed genes (depth-filtered ≥ 10). Heat-mediated DEGs were determined using DESeq2 (v.1.44.0) (Love et al., 2014) and R software (v4.4.1) for the investigated time points (3, 7, 13 dps) in both varieties (Wald-test; padj ≤ 0.05 (BH); $|\log_2FC| \geq 1$; depth-filtered ≥ 10 to remove weakly expressed genes). Similar cut-offs were used to determine constitutively differentially expressed genes between Solara and Cecile under control temperatures (Wald-test; padj ≤ 0.05 (BH); $|\log_2FC| \geq 1$; depth-filtered ≥ 10). No distinction was made between the different time points (3, 7, 13 dps).

GO-term enrichment analysis was performed as described recently (Kaier et al., 2024) using the Bioconductor package clusterProfiler (v4.12.6) and R software (v4.4.1) (Wu et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2012). Enrichments with Bonferroni ≤ 0.05 were accepted as significant.

In addition to the functional categorization by GO ontology, MapMan was also used (Usadel et al., 2005): Stub_PGSC_DM_v3.4 is available to download from: <https://mapman.gabipd.org> and was blasted against DM 1–3516 R44 potato v6.1. *Solanum tuberosum* genes were described by their best *A. thaliana* or *Solanum lycopersicum* hit based on BLASTP similarity. Unless stated otherwise, the annotation from the reference genome DM potato v6.1 has been used. To make the investigation of individual pathways as clear as possible, genes with weak expression were excluded more strictly than in previous analyses. Unless otherwise stated, the data were depth-filtered ≥ 50 .

Plots were generated using the ggplot2 package (v3.5.1) in R.

5.7. Quantitative PCR

To verify gene expression patterns observed in the RNA-Seq analysis, qPCR was conducted. To this end, cDNA was synthesized from 1 μ g DNaseI-treated total RNA using oligo dT30 primer. The qPCR was essentially performed as described by Ferreira et al., (2010) using gene specific primers (see Suppl. Table 7). Ubiquitin (L22576) was used as reference gene according to (Kloosterman et al., 2007). Relative expression levels were calculated according to Livak and Schmittgen (2001).

5.8. Statistics

Statistical analyses were performed using R software (v4.4.1) to assess differences between control and heat conditions in both varieties at different dps. Data were tested for normality and homogeneity of variance. For normally distributed data, an unpaired Welch *t*-test

(default) was performed as the variances were mostly heterogeneous. In cases where there was a prior hypothesis based on literature and preliminary experiments, a one-tailed, unpaired Welch *t*-test was performed (see figure captions). When data were not normally distributed, a non-parametric Wilcoxon rank sum test was used.

All *p*-values were adjusted for multiple testing to control the false discovery rate (fdr, Benjamini-Hochberg), separately for each trait analyzed (e.g., tuber weight, individual amino acids and hormones, etc.).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Selina Beck: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Luisa Höfner:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **David Rüscher:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Danuše Tarkowská:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jitka Široká:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Stephen Reid:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **David Pscheidt:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jörg Hofmann:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ondřej Novák:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Miroslav Strnad:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Sophia Sonnewald:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Consent for publication

All authors agree to publish.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jplph.2025.154683>.

Data availability

The raw sequencing data are stored under the BioProject ID PRJNA1322102 in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA1322102>. All used relevant scripts are

available on github: https://github.com/Division-of-Biochemistry-Publications/DFG_HotNet.

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